

Sailors of the network: hackers and cypherpunks in comparison

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Workgroup 30 “Infrastructure is something you can kick” – Hacking on Media Infrastructure

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Introduction

Infrastructures represent the substructure that regulates our lives. They are invisible, nevertheless they provide essential services to current society. The subversion of infrastructures operated by hackers usually makes them visible and alters the planned use of their original design, giving these infrastructures a new meaning and scope. The purpose, ideals, and motives of the hackers are not always known or understood by the public: their work is often considered a crime, an invasion of a protected space that is nothing but a vandalistic act. Moreover, the culture of the hackers is often confused with that of cypherpunks: both movements are considered the same side of the same coin, although having very distant perspectives.

The aim of this paper is to dig deeper into the differences between the two groups and into their understanding of the concept of infrastructure, which - I claim - is significantly divergent. By taking a closer look at the imaginaries they believe in and the missions they perpetuate, I suggest that while the hackers address the idea of decentralized systems, cypherpunks promote distributed services (e.g., Bitcoin); this disposition posits the two groups as polar opposites. However, I argue that, even if their ideals are different, some of their purposes bring them together in the primary contestation of governments and organizations' control over the network.

Theoretical Framework

Popular culture is often unaware of the real significance of hacking and its purpose. Therefore, an elucidation of this movement is necessary for a clearer differentiation between the aforementioned group and cypherpunks. By the term 'hacking', we refer to the appropriation or modification of "technology-infused systems, often in a playful or exploratory way ... to improve performance or create an application that differs from the device's original purpose" (Paradiso, Heidemann and Zimmerman 2008, 13). Hackers are often motivated by democratic and empowering ideals. Their core values, embedded in deep-rooted libertarianism, include freedom, individualism, meritocracy, and the right to privacy (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016).

Even though over time their culture intertwined with the cypherpunks' movement (Taylor 1999), the two groups were originally distinct (Levy 2001). Despite the innovative and lively disposition that brings cypherpunks closer to the earlier hacker cultures (Levy

1984), the formers represent a trend on their own. Anderson (2022) situates cypherpunks “under a technical definition of data activism” (7). It engages with datafication and surveillance and considers privacy and transparency as co-dependent concepts (Anderson 2022).

Differences between hackers and cypherpunks widen as we look at the imaginaries they believe in. The liberal ideals driving hackers also resonate in the open imaginary that originates from the free code movement, which “places source code in the realm of freedom” (Coleman 2013, 44). It calls for open technologies, accessible to everyone and on which no one has exclusive property rights (Coleman 2013). The type of freedom hackers look for is a positive freedom, one that *enables* to use technology (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016). Instead, cypherpunks as crypto enthusiasts look for a negative freedom that values privacy and encryption, and which is therefore “freedom *from* others” (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016, 1105). Swartz (2018) calls this techno-economic imaginary that originates in the cypherpunk movements “infrastructural mutualism” (632).

Both movements have a different understanding of communication networks. Baran (1964) explains the three possible interpretations of these networks: centralized, decentralized, and distributed. Whilst centralized networks are vulnerable due to their dependence on the central node, decentralized systems rely on a hierarchical structure “of a set of stars connected in the form of a larger star with an additional link forming a loop” (Baran 1964, 1). In this case, nodes do not always rely on the focal point (Baran 1964). The independent nature of decentralized systems suits more the needs of the hackers, who value individuality and autonomy (Bravo 2017).

On the other hand, decentralized systems still represent an unsafe network: “destruction of a small number of nodes ... can destroy communication” (Baran 1964, 1). The cypherpunks’ culture has always been oriented towards an even stronger model of communication: the distributed systems. In distributed systems all stations are interconnected and do not rely on a central node; there are no vulnerabilities (Baran 1964). This system of communication has later been defined as “federated network” (Mostafei et al. 2020), further highlighting its sharing-oriented layout. For example, the Internet, with its packet-switching technology, represents a distributed system, which is difficult to censor by central authorities (Deibert and Stein 2003). The purpose of cypherpunks to protect privacy can only be fulfilled

by the technology of distributed systems, which uses encryption to protect information (Swartz 2018).

Method

The analysis conducted in this paper aims at providing a broader and clearer image of the purposes and ideals of hackers and cypherpunks as distinct groups. For this study, I focused on what is considered to be the hackers' Bible, the book "Hackers: Heroes of the Computer Revolution" by Steven Levy (1984). I also analyzed part of the "Cyphernomicon" (May 1994) and of the book "Cypherpunks: Freedom and the Future of the Internet" (Assange et al. 2012) to obtain an insider's perspective on the cypherpunks' culture. I also referred to "The Californian Ideology" (Barbrook and Cameron 1996), as one of the main inspirations for political debate among hackers, and to the "Declaration of Independence of Cyberspace", written by the cypherpunk and co-founder of Electronic Frontier Foundation John Perry Barlow (1996). Finally, I employed "A Cypherpunk's Manifesto" (Hughes 1993) to further disassemble the group's ideology.

My analysis is primarily textual: the most significant elements of the analyzed sources were picked apart to get interpreted and located into the theoretical framework provided. The message and aim of relevant statements were associated to tendencies and imaginaries to further prove the difference of position of the two groups. Subsequently, similar orientations were identified to acknowledge similarities between hackers and cypherpunks.

Analysis

Classifying the cypherpunks' movement under the rubric of hackers distorts the interpretation of the essence of both groups (Anderson 2022). Their ethics, epistemology, and imaginaries differ to a large extent, even though both groups are covered under the label of anti-hegemonic organizations (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016). The three intrinsic assets that differentiate them are the followings: 1) hackers and cypherpunks fall under different definitions and cultures; 2) their disposition towards - and understanding of - infrastructures is divergent; 3) the imaginaries that motive them are clashing.

Independent matrices

The genesis and development of both groups follow autonomous tracks. The first hackers are considered to be phone phreakers, individuals who broke through the first mobile

communication systems with the main purpose of exploring the network (Lapsley and Wozniak 2013). Computer hacking, however, began more or less in the same time period (Levy 1984). Hacking means learning about an infrastructure and trying to remake it, exploit it, or improve it (Levy 1984). Dysfunctional systems “infuriate hackers, whose primal instinct is to debug them” (Levy 1984, 24). Their inner motif is therefore that of understanding how a system works, and what can be done to make it functions better, with the user as the primary beneficiary in mind.

Even though revolutionary and anti-statist (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016), the hacker culture is not as rooted in the anarchist paradigm as the cypherpunks’ movement. Indeed, the latter group has far more subversive ideals: May (1984) himself defines crypto-anarchy, considered an integral current of the cypherpunks’ movement, as “a throwback to the pre-state days of individual choice about which laws to follow” (May 1984). The cypherpunks’ priorities in their battle against the law and regulations are defined in their Manifesto: privacy, anonymity, cryptography (Hughes 1993).

Different network models

Hackers and cypherpunks adopt different attitudes towards media infrastructures, first because the communication network that they consider the safest is different for both groups and even contradictory. Hackers “promote decentralization” (Levy 1984, 25) since it represents the easiest way to exchange information freely (Levy 1984). These networks have no boundaries and are therefore suitable for “the exploratory impulse of true hackers” (Levy 1984, 25). The individuality of nodes in decentralized systems additionally reflects the isolated nature of the hacker, who is often depicted as “a lone individual fighting for survival within the virtual world of information” (Barbrook and Cameron 1996, 20).

The preference of cypherpunks for distributed networks is even clearer: indeed, they declare themselves sustainers of cryptography (Hughes 1993). When in 1993 interest in this technology increased and the Cypherpunks mailing list was formed, the foundations for the Bitcoin cryptocurrency were laid (Swartz 2018). Notoriously, Bitcoin is possible thanks to its “distributed ledger-keeping protocol (the blockchain)” (Swartz 2018, 629). Nodes in distributed networks are tied to no central core: they are autonomous and safely connected. Barlow (1996) further highlights the importance of the absence of constrictions in cyberspace. His denunciation of governments and his call for independence and freedom

recalls the memorable “Declaration of Independence” by Thomas Jefferson (1776). Just like the Founding Fathers of the United States declared their land free from the United Kingdom, Barlow (1996) states that the people of cyberspace are independent from governments, which have no sovereignty online. Moreover, addressing such a paper, written by a promoter of federation like Jefferson, remarks the cypherpunks’ call for distributed networks of communication, which, namely, are also called federated (Mostafei et al. 2020).

Contrasting imaginaries

Sociotechnical imaginaries of hackers and cypherpunks also happen to be quite divergent. As a matter of fact, hacking understood as subverting infrastructures to obtain an innovative outcome out of their original design is tied to the imaginary of “open technology” (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016, 113). Indeed, the first imperative of the hacker ethic cites: “Access to computer ... should be unlimited and total” (Levy 1984, 23). Hackers believe that the only way to fix or improve a technology is to have access to all the possible information about it (Levy 1984). “Closed” technologies are perceived as problematic since they prevent implementation and transformation (Wagenknecht and Korn 2016, 113).

Contrastingly, the promotion of encryption by cypherpunks disposes them towards closed forms of freedom, which ensure privacy. Indeed, the imaginary that originates from this movement is that of infrastructural mutualism, rooted in “the ideology of privacy and mutualistic self-help organized through ‘writing code’” (Swartz 2018, 632). In contrast to the hackers’ open imaginary that addresses freedom of information, cypherpunks state: “we must ensure that we reveal as little as possible” (Hughes 1993, 1). Their devotion to code and anonymity (Hughes 1993), therefore, cannot match the hacker’s desire for an open-source society of free software (Tkacz 2012).

Discussion – a shared effort for change

Despite the evident differences between the cypherpunks and the hackers, both groups share the core value of independence, which posits them in open opposition to the tendency of the state to use the Internet as a “cutting-edge instrument of surveillance and repression” (Maxigas 2017, 11). They work for a future in which there are no inequalities, and in which everyone can express his thoughts and beliefs freely (Barlow 1996; Levy 1984). The fight against authorities, which classifies both movements as anarchist and anti-statist

(Wagenknecht and Korn 2016) is justified by the desire to erase the “legal concepts” owned by governments “of property, expression, identity and context” (Barlow 1996).

Both cypherpunks and hackers address similar mottos: “Privacy for the weak and transparency for the powerful” (Assange et al. 2012) for the former group, and “make public data available, protect private data” (Chaos Computer Club) for the latter, which is an addition to hacker’s ethic from the CCC collective. Through these slogans, both groups want to make clear that their help is offered to users, seen as unaware victims under the control of institutions, who instead constitute the primary objective of their attacks and revolt.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to trace the main differences between the hackers’s and the cypherpunks’ cultures as for their characteristics, aim, and infrastructural imaginaries. This interpretative analysis showed how both groups should be understood under different definitions, and the way each defines networks and technologies is contrasting. A closer look at the papers they mainly refer to revealed that while hacker culture is rooted in the curiosity of playing with systems’ rules and subverting them, cypherpunks are more politically-oriented toward an anarchic revolution of current order through encryption and code for the protection of privacy. However, my analysis also highlighted how they share an interest in the safeguard of users’ data and an aversion to governments and laws. Further research could dig deeper into the dialogue between cypherpunks and hackers, how their ideas intertwined, and whether hybrid groups exist today.

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